

A NESTED INFINITE RADICAL EXPRESSION FOR ODD NUMBERS

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Abstract

I am going to provide a Nested Infinite Radical Expression for all Odd Numbers greater than 1. Along with that, I will also prove the Proposition mentioned by various methods.

1 Introduction

Srinivasa Ramanujan proposed a nested infinite radical problem in JIMS (Journal of the Indian Mathematical Society). The problem (Q.289) says Find the value of :

$$\sqrt{1 + 2\sqrt{1 + 3\sqrt{1 + \dots}}} \quad (1)$$

Ramanujan gave the solution of the above problem as 3. I have tried to create some similar series like this and later generalized it for all odd numbers greater than 1.

Proposition 1. *For all odd numbers (in the form $2k-1$) greater than 1 we have*

$$2k - 1 = \sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k - 1)\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k)\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}} \quad (2)$$

Later in the paper, I will also provide some strong proofs using the generalization of nested expression given by Srinivasa Ramanujan, along with that I will also show that how any odd numbers can be transformed into a nested infinite expression and vice versa.

2 Generalization

I begin by proving Proposition 1,

$$2k - 1 = \sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k - 1)\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k)\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}}$$

Proof. From the generalization of (1) given by Srinivasa Ramanujan, i.e.

$$\sqrt{ax + (n + a)^2 + x\sqrt{a(x + n) + (n + a)^2 + (x + n)\sqrt{\dots}}} = x + n + a \quad (3)$$

if we set $a = 0$, $x = k^2 - k - 1$, and $n = 1$ we get,

$$\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k - 1)\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k)\sqrt{1 + \dots}}} = k^2 - k$$

After some algebraic manipulation we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k - 1)\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k)\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}} &= \sqrt{1 + 4(k^2 - k)} \\ \Rightarrow \sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k - 1)\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k)\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}} &= \sqrt{(2k - 1)^2} \\ \Rightarrow \sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k - 1)\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k)\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}} &= (2k - 1) \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

and this completes our proof. Now I will provide some example which would help us understand the need of the formula (2).

Example 2.1 Find a nested radical expression for : i) 131 ii) 729

Solution. i) To find the required expression we first set

$$2k - 1 = 131 \Rightarrow k = 66$$

Now, using (2) we get,

$$131 = \sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + 4289\sqrt{1 + 4290\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}}$$

ii) Again, to find the required expression we first set

$$2k - 1 = 729 \Rightarrow k = 365$$

Now, using (2) we get,

$$729 = \sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + 132859\sqrt{1 + 132860\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}} \quad (4)$$

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Example 2.2 Find the value of :

$$\sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + 65279\sqrt{1 + 65280\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}}$$

Solution. Now to solve this we need to compare this with (2),

$$\sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + \underbrace{65279}_{=k^2-k-1}\sqrt{1 + 65280\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}}$$

$$\text{So, } k^2 - k - 1 = 65279$$

$$\Rightarrow k = 256$$

or

$$\Rightarrow k = -255$$

Since k is positive so our final value for k is 256 and thus our final answer is 511. ◀

3 The Famous Problem

Now I will show how we can use the above-mentioned formula to solve the problem given by Srinivasa Ramanujan, i.e.

$$\text{Let, } S = \sqrt{1 + 2\sqrt{1 + 3\sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + 5\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}}}$$

On comparing with (2) we get,

$$\sqrt{1 + 2\sqrt{1 + 3\sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + 5\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}}} = \sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k - 1)\sqrt{1 + (k^2 - k)\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}}$$

$$\Rightarrow k^2 - k - 1 = 5$$

$$\Rightarrow k = 3$$

or,

$$\Rightarrow k = -2$$

Since k is positive so our final value for k is 3, Now on moving back to our original equation we get,

$$\Rightarrow \sqrt{1 + 2\sqrt{1 + 3\sqrt{1 + 4\sqrt{1 + 5\sqrt{1 + \dots}}}}}_{=2(3)-1}$$

$$\Rightarrow S = \sqrt{1 + 2\sqrt{1 + 3 \cdot 5}} = \sqrt{1 + 2\sqrt{16}} = \sqrt{1 + 2 \cdot 4} = \sqrt{9} = 3 \quad \square$$

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References

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